

Work done in the context of the CardioNIR project: CARDIOvascular Near-InfraRed spectroscopy probing - PTDC/EMD-EMD/3822/2021.

Annex 1: Data gathering.

Table 1: Number of samples and spectra already collected from different sources.

Origin	Experiment	No. of patients	No. of samples	No. of spectra DBS	No. of Spectra collected during surgery
CT Surgery	NA	16	63	1040	1054
Experimental Surgery	#2	1	11	226	25
Experimental Surgery	#3	1	28	574	797
AVC/Stroke/Aortic Stenosis	NA	27	54	1080	NA

ANNEX 2: Pictures were taken during large animal surgery

Figure 1: Bypass machine

Figures 2-3: Surgical procedures

Figures 4-6: Surgical procedures

Figures 6-9: NIR spectra acquisition directly on the myocardium of the animal. Inset, one can spot the hand-held NIRS equipment.

ANNEX 3: Response surface plots for Design Of Experiment (DOE)

Figure 10: Response surface plot in DOE to optimize protein extraction conditions from DBS (dried blood spots) cards. Protein concentration plotted in function of time and temperature of extraction in an extraction of $\frac{1}{4}$ of a DBS blood spot using 50mM of ammonium bicarbonate.

ANNEX 4: Preliminary Results

Figure 11: Scores Scatter plot of PCA of NIR spectra of AVC and Aortic Stenosis (EAO) samples.

Figures 12-13: Loadings plot of PC2 showing the molecular fingerprint responsible for discrimination between AVC and Aortic stenosis samples in Scores Scatter plot of Figure 10.